

Light is Bending Space-Time – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework which regard bosonic propagations as net curvature on a varying Lorenz manifold, (M, g_E) with signature $(3,1)$, which is the connected manifold, $M = M_0 \times R$, invoked stationary, by the Euler Lagrange operator, it is possible to derive new insight regarding the nature of boson, and in contradiction to what is now known, light is not bended by matter, but matter is banding toward light. To proof that such is the case, the author will use the coupling constant series.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.11)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.12)$$

By putting the Lorentz manifold in Euler- LaGrange framework and allowing arbitrary variations to appear, in which we require to vanish, in the 8T we discretized and partitioned the term (1.14) and were able to prove that arbitrary variations of the manifold vanish into matter. Each net variation or net curvature is isomorphic to a bosonic field propagation. In particular the boson associated with photon propagation is $N_V = +(5)$. Such propagation is than yielding a positive summation, i.e. a positive curvature by (1.15), so fermion clusters are flat according to the 8T framework, but bosonic propagations are curvature on the manifold. The weird and unexpected result is that bosonic fields are deflecting fermion clusters and not the opposite as believed by GR. It is an unexpected result, but up until recently we thought there are only four forces, and such thought lead to thinking that physics can be unified.

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial \delta g'}{\partial \partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.13)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.14)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i > 0 \quad (1.15)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.16)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)